
A NEW SUBSPECIES OF *AGAPANTHIA (EPOPTES) BOEBERI* (FISCHER VON WALDHEIM, 1806) (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE) FROM TURKEY

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ABSTRACT: *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi chorumensis* ssp. n. is described from Turkey (Chorum prov.). The new taxon is not close to any other subspecies of *A. (E.) boeberi*. The species was not definitely known from Anatolia before (Sama, 2003).

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, distribution, new subspecies, Turkey

A revision of *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806) taxonomy was recently published (Lazarev, 2023). Six subspecies were accepted; one new subspecies was described as *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi slamai* Lazarev, 2023 and one old synonym was validated as: *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927.

1. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi boeberi* (Fischer von Waldheim, 1806)
Type locality. Russia, "Sarepta" - south suburbs of Volgograd.
2. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi selengensis* Danilevsky, 2021
Type locality. Russia, Transbaikalia, Novoselenginsk environs.
3. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi cynarae* (Germar, 1817)
Type locality. Dalmatia and Sicily ("bei Fiume und auf der Insel Arbe", "bei Spalato, Ragusa und Cattaro in Dalmatien").
4. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi diversicornis* Pic, 1927
Type locality. Albania.
5. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi slamai* Lazarev, 2023
Type locality. Greece, Peloponnese, Kariopolis, near Gythion.
6. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi michaeli* Sláma, 1986
Type locality. Crete, Voutas.

Now my good friend Sergey Murzin submitted me for study a series of very interesting *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi* from Chorum province of Turkey not similar to any other known before. It is described below as a new subspecies. The species was not known before from Anatolia. Many old records for Anatolia listed by Özdikmen, 2007: 347, 392 (Bilecik, Içel, Amasya, Bursa, Erzurum, Konya, Akşehir, Kocaeli, İzmit) were ignored by Sama (2003).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material was collected manually. Specimens used in morphological studies were killed by ethyl acetate. All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow)

OP - collection of O.V. Pak (Donetsk)

SM - collection of S.V. Murzin (Moscow)

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University

RESULTS

Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi chorumensis ssp. n.

(Figs. 1-2)

Type locality. Turkey, Çorum province, Çorum environs.

Description. Small subspecies; antennae relatively short, about one third longer than the body in males, surpassing elytral apex by 5 antennal joints in males or 4 in female; black 3rd antennal joint widely lightened basally; about apical halves of 4th - 12th joints black, basal halves reddish; setae tuft of 3rd joint absent, but several long apical setae present; prothorax transverse, strongly widened basally; pronotum with wide and dense central and lateral yellow stripes, without yellow pubescence in between, with shining black cuticula, modified by dense rugose punctation; elytra in males about 3 times longer than wide, in female - about 2.7 times; long erect setae distinct at elytral bases only; grey humeral elytral stripe well developed; elytral setae spots indistinct; elytral apices angulated; body length in males: 13.2-14.8 mm, body width: 3.3-4.0 mm, body length in female: 13.4 mm, body width: 3.2 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon differs from the nominative subspecies (Lazarev, 2023) as well as from all other subspecies of *A. (E.) boeberi* by presence of grey humeral elytral stripe.

Type material. Holotype (Fig. 1), male, Turkey, Çorum province, Çorum environs, 18.6.1994, N. Auvray leg. - ML; 4 paratypes (ML & SM); 2 males, 1 female with same label; 1 female (Fig. 2), Turkey, Çorum province, Çorum environs, 24.6.1995, C. Auvray leg.

Material used for comparison. *Agapanthia (Epoptes) boeberi boeberi*: 3 males, 2 females, Chechnya, Starogladkovskaya, Terek River, 22-23.6.1928, Arnoldi - MD; 7 males, 2 females, Russia, Kuban, Mingrelskaya, 10.5.1939, V. Galkin leg. - ZMM; 1 female, N. Cauc., Mt. Beshtau, 6.1924 - ZMM; 1 female, Russia, Ural - ZMM; 1 female, Dagestan, Kizlyar - ZMM; 1 male, Russia, Samara region, Nikolaevsk distr., 16.7.1911 - ZMM; 1 male, Stavropol region, Pokoinoe, 10.7.1914, L. Bankovsky leg. - ZMM; 1 male, Orenburg Region, Sol-Iletsk District, Troitsk environs, 20-30.6.2007, D. Shavkun - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Orenburg Region, Sol-Iletsk District, 8 km SW Troitsk, 21.05.2012, A. Shapovalov - OP; 1 male, 1 female, Orenburg Region, Gay District, Khmelevka, 12.6.2008, A. Shapovalov - ML; 2 males, 1 female, Chelyabinsk Region, S. Troitsk, Zolotaya

Sopka, 54°02'46"N, 61°36'34"E, 4-6.6.2013, E.Yu. Zakharova - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Kazakhstan, Uralsk, Rozhkovo, 100 m, 15.6.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD.

Four specimens from "Transcaucasia" could be with wrong labels: 1 male, "Azerbaidzhan / Chatschmas / 7.VII.[1]933 / F. Lukjanovihh" - ZMM; 1 female, "Tanscaucas" - ZMM; 1 male, "Caucasus / Kakheta / 6.7." - ZMM; 1 male, Mtskheta, 16.5.1911 - ZMM.

Distribution. Only one population known in north-west Anatolia, Çorum environs.

Etymology. The name of the new taxon is derived from the name of the type locality.

Figures 1-2. *Agapanthia (Epopetes) boeberi chorumensis* ssp. n.: 1 – Holotype, male, Turkey, Çorum province, Çorum environs, 18.6.1994, N. Auvray leg.; 2- Paratype, female, Turkey, Çorum province, Çorum environs, 24.6.1995, C. Auvray leg.

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